

Spectrophotometric Study of Copper-2-Methyl-4-Thiazolyl Benzoyl Ketoxime Complex

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2-Methyl-4-thiazolylbenzoyl ketoxime forms green complex with Cu^{+2} which is completely extracted in chloroform. Spectrophotometric study was made at various pH values and Job's method of continuous variation was applied at pH 6 to find out the mole ratio.

2-Methyl-4-thiazolylbenzoyl ketoxime was prepared by the method described by Bhagwat and Nargund¹. The recrystallised compound is pale brown solid, m.p. 171–172°. The product is insoluble in water and soluble in common organic solvents.

All the chemicals used in solvent extraction process were of B.D.H. "Analar" quality.

$10^{-3} M$ CuSO_4 solution was prepared as stock solution. $10^{-3} M$ reagent solution was prepared in chloroform. A suitable volume of Cu^{+2} solution was diluted to $10^{-4} M$. pH of these solutions were adjusted by using suitable buffers. Equal volumes of Cu^{+2} solution and reagent solution in chloroform (with Cu^{+2} : Reagent ratio as 1 : 10) were shaken in separating funnels. The extent of extraction of complex in chloroform layer was studied spectrophotometrically at different time intervals. It was observed, that, at pH 6, the complex gets nearly completely extracted within half an hour.

Chloroform extracts of complex at various pH were investigated spectrophotometrically between 600–340 $m\mu$ with appropriate blanks. In all the cases the maximum absorbance was at 360 $m\mu$.

Spectrophotometric measurements were made on Beckmann D.U. spectrophotometer, Model G 2400. pH were adjusted on Beckmann pH meter, Model G with accuracy of ± 0.01 pH units. All the measurements were made at 25°.

The results of the above investigation are shown in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1

Job's method of continuous variation : From Figure 1, it is clear that maximum absorbance was in the region of pH 6. Therefore, pH 6 was selected for finding out the mole ratio. The absorbance was studied at 360 m μ .

Varying volumes of equimolar ($10^{-3} M$) solution of Cu^{+2} in water and reagent in chloroform were mixed keeping the total volume constant (20 ml; 10 ml each). The data is shown in Table I.

TABLE I

	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X
Reagent ($10^{-3}M$) in $CHCl_3$ ml.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Chloroform, ml	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0
Cu^{+2} ($10^{-3}M$) ml.	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0
Water ml.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
O.D (corrected)	0.3092	0.5984	0.8826	1.1368	1.3710	1.5652	1.3994	0.9536	0.5078	0.0000

The O.D. of chloroform extract of complex in each case was then recorded using appropriate blank. Corrected O.D. are plotted against corresponding volumes of Cu^{+2} and reagent. The result is shown in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2

From the plot, the ratio, metal : ligand is 3.65 : 6.35, i.e., 1 : 2.

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